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Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

Reclaiming Justice : A Review of Fali S. Nariman's India's Legal System: Can it be Saved

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Sanjeev Kumar Chadha

Professor
Department Of Law
Babasaheb Bhimrao
Ambedkar Central University
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh,
India,

Mahak Rajpal

Student (B.B.A.-LL.B.)
Department Of Law
ALS-Amity University
Rajasthan, India

Karan Choudhary

Student (B.A-L.LB)
Department Of Law
University of Rajasthan
Rajasthan, India

Abhishek Srivastava

Assistant Professor
Department Of Law
ALS-Amity University
Rajasthan, India

Abstract

This is the book review of "India's Legal System- Can it be saved?" by "Fali S. Nariman" which is a well-researched, elaborative and with some legal technicalities, this book offers valuable insights into how the system has evolved over time, its historical context, present challenges, and future prospects making this book time and knowledge worthy. This book simultaneously deals with the drawbacks of our legal system, the problem of English common law, overwhelming backlog of cases and the prolonged and costly nature of trials. In the overview of this book the author presents both critiques and analyses, offering readers a balanced perspective to help discern what may be right or wrong in the system and moreover how to save the India's legal system? With this overview we delve deeper into the history of legal system, it's inconsistencies and to improve that system with a message to third millennium to not to lose the savor of salt of Earth which is Judiciary of our country.

Keywords India's Legal System, Rule of Law, Constitutional Democracy, Separation of Power, Judicial Accountability, Legal Reforms.

Introduction

"Justice in the life and conduct of the State is possible only as first it resides in the hearts and souls of the citizens."

— Plato

The judiciary is like the oxygen in the air- citizens simply do not realize and comprehend its utility and importance.[1] We take it for granted.[2] In vast country like ours which is governed by law which is "rule of law" and with "the second largest legal profession in the world" we need to realize the dire need to understand our legal system and not just the legal professionals should understand it but every common man of this country who use, learn and live in the environment of a country governed and directed by constitution. Common man of this country, today are trapped in this chaotic system of "Justice" which provides everything except justice! The legal system which should have the pursuit of truth only finds what's the proof?

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Formation of this legal system from the Ancient India time to today has lost many valuable norms and essence of what justice is and about what law is. The attempt of this book is to put forth the shortcomings of India's legal system, the chaotic legal system, the valuable history, the complex common law, the conflict between legislature and judiciary, the use and misuse of articles-32[3], 136[4], 142[5], 226[6] lack of consistency in courts and the solution of those problems.

A brief summary of the work and its contributions to the existing and expanding body of legal knowledge will be given in the second part. Before carefully assessing the work's value in relation to the existing legal framework, we have made an effort to analyze its organization and conceptual development. In the third part, the critique shall be followed by the conclusion.

Objective of study

This is the book review of "India's Legal System- Can it be saved?" by "Fali S. Nariman" which is a well-researched, elaborative and with some legal technicalities, this book offers valuable insights into how the system has evolved over time, its historical context, present challenges, and future prospects making this book time and knowledge worthy.

Review of Literature

This paper is based on the review of various literature which is discussed through out the main text.

Main Text

Overview and Contributions

Against the backdrop of various news, reports, events and interviews like- "Thirty four judges handle an overwhelming load of nearly seventy thousand appeals and petitions, issuing some thousand judgements every year"[7], "*More than fifty million cases are pending across the country, according to the National Judicial Data Grid — a pileup that has doubled over the past two decades*"[8]. "Kiran Rijiju also revealed that more than 69,000 cases were as yet undecided in the supreme court, with nearly six million in the country's Twenty five high courts – possibly the world's highest number.[9] A 2018 analysis by the government-run Niti Aayog public policy think tank estimated that it would take 324 years to clear India's overall backlog of judicial cases." [10] The author's contribution to this field is highly commendable; moreover, if the solutions proposed in the book are implemented, there is a strong possibility of saving our judicial system.

A. Chapterisation and overview

The book is divided into Eleven chapters. The first, titled '*The legal system in pre-British India*'[11], provides "*how ancient India were governed by moral law*", how law developed by various smritis, Dharmashastras, then Arthashastra and how Manusmriti played the major role in formation of law. In the second chapter '*The functioning of the legal system in British India and its transition into independent India*'[12], author has introduced about the judicial system in India before Britishers which was established by Mughal emperors including several courts like; mofussil dewanny adawlat, sudder dewanny adawlat, sudder nizamat adawlat etc.

In the third and fourth chapter '*The legal system at village level*'[13], and '*Misgivings about the British legal system, and harkening back to panchayati raj*'[14], author told grave misgivings about the legal system we inherited nurtured during eve of independence and followers of Mahatma Gandhi told to re-organize the village panchayats. "*Their efforts to constitute polity based on village autonomy and self-sufficiency were not accepted by constituent assembly*". [15]

In the fifth chapter '*The legal system under the constitution of India, and the link with the English language*'[16] author expresses about the adoption of Constitution, federal and bicameral structure stating further the system of rulings by Supreme court of the country and the issue of writs and the adoption of English language as language of India.

In the sixth and seventh chapter "*Some 'new trunks'-alternative methods of dispute resolution outside the established court system*"[17] and "*Some impressions of justice in British India*"[18] author has introduced the various alternate dispute resolution methods like conciliation and arbitration, Lok adalats and specialized tribunals rather than the exhausting process of court and author has expressed about the concept of "*Justice, equity and good conscience*" with the explanation of carved stones depiction in the magnificent Bombay high court building.

In the eighth chapter "*The different aspects of justice under the constitution*" [19] author expressed his views on various different topics stated; justice in the constitution, special provision for SC,ST and backward classes as part of social justice, abolition of untouchability and its history, criticizing the DPSP (directive principles of state policy) for not being enforceable against the state.

In the ninth chapter "*The criminal justice system*"[20] author talks about the administration of criminal law stating the problem of continuous increase in the number of crimes and less number of judges. Author further stated some host of other problems with criminal law in India and how it is administered, which are; out of date laws,[21] no elaborate strategy in place for compensating sufferers of crime,[22] obligatory confinement for certain offenses is not a viable option,[23] The right to silence,[24] Lack of an ideal crime-control model,[25] Fallibility of judges at different level,[26] The '*proof-beyond-reasonable doubt*' standard,[27] Affluent and cunning people are adept at "*manipulating*" the inquiry and "*managing*" the proof that exists.[28]

In the penultimate chapter "*Who services the Indian legal system, and how effectively?*"[29] author talks about the pros and cons of Indian legal system stating that; in terms of recommended judge strength, the sanctioned judge strength, especially at the subordinate and high court levels, continues to be abysmally low.

In the eleventh chapter "*The Indian legal system-some problem areas*" author talks about the various problems of India's legal system which are; "*Proliferation of appeals*,"[30] "*Judicial interference in administrative actions*,"[31] "*Judicial attitudes-a lack of consistency by the court at the highest level*,"[32] "*Suggestions for judicial reforms*": they must not face problems from the judiciary itself.[33]

B. Summary

To begin the summary, it is crucial to note that the book does not focus solely on a single issue; instead, it addresses a range of subtopics essential to understand the collapse of India's legal system. Initially, the book explores the legal framework in pre-British India.[34] In next chapter author has showed the transition of legal system from British to independent India which consisted of various charters and the earlier establishment of courts by Mughals to their decline followed by the British legal system. This period saw the formation of three foundational codes: India incorporated elements of common law and enacted key legal codes, including the "Code of Civil Procedure (1859), the Indian Penal Code (1860), and the Code of Criminal Procedure (1861)", shaping its judicial framework.

The author Further discusses about the legal system at village level and shows how the British innovated Arbitration has impacted but not infiltrated the panchayat system and the Britishers has respected the judgements by the panchayats and has generally refrained to intervened. In the next chapter author explains the link of English language with the constitution and legal system under it. In this chapter author opines on importance of Article 14[35], 17[36], 32[37], 226[38] and has stated that how an English oak tree in Indian soil has turned into large Indian banyan tree.

The author Further discusses about the different aspects of justice under the constitution.[39] He questions '*are the elected representatives of the people- the state legislatures and parliament- the sole repositories of the justice of the laws they enact? In other words, what about plainly arbitrary laws?*'[40]. Further author

discusses about the concept of *intelligible differentia* or the '*classification test*'. Ordinarily, in India, substantive laws cannot and ought not to be struck down because the courts regard them as '*unjustified*' or '*unreasonable*' per se.[41]

In next chapter author discuss about the situation and problem of criminal justice in India.[42] In "*Law, Poverty and Legal Aid: Access to Criminal Justice*", the author, Mr. S. Murlidhar[43] has provided a ready reckoner of the scenario. In all central jails where the number of prisoners that can be accommodated is 1,59,158, the actual number held is 1,85,182 (116.4 % over the full occupancy rate), including 94,675 undertrial prisoners (51.1 %) (2015 data).[44] Further authors talks about the various recommendations of Malimath committee and their application and goes on to the detail of various problems which provides in-depth knowledge of the problems and their solution like author discusses the; Section 53 of the Indian Penal Code 1860[45], article 20(3) of Indian constitution[46], 'right to silence', beyond a 'reasonable doubt' concept, 'section 311 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of 1973'.[47]

In the penultimate chapter author discusses who services the Indian legal system, and how effectively?[48] Legal professionals and judges are the primary providers of services for the intricate civil and criminal legal systems that operate in post-independence India under the auspices of a written Constitution that protects basic rights and claims to ensure justice for its inhabitants.[49] "The report of committee recommended the acceptance, in the first instance of increasing the judge strength[50] to fifty judges per ten lakh people, as had been recommended by the 120th Law Commission Report".[51] While discussing the Advocates act of 1961 author states that Following the act's passage, only a specific group of people has been permitted to practice law, namely advocates (under section 29[52]), and only citizens of India can be enrolled as advocates (under section 24[53]).[54] Thereafter author discusses about the legal profession that today we have been using our skills not in a profession but in a game, in which the more skillful will invariably win! Great legal theorist Dean Roscoe Pound described as the 'sporting theory of justice', The fundamental idea behind it is basically 'truth will prevail in the clash of Zealous adversaries'.[55]

In the final chapter author examines some problematic areas of the Indian legal system.[56] Starting with the proliferation of appeals book states 'The portion about no man having a right to unlimited draughts on the time and money of the public in order to get his private affairs settled as he wished' was quoted by Justice Gajendragadkar (who later became Chief Justice of India) in one of the early reports of the Law Commission of India,[57] However, our laws still provide for unrestricted access to the public's time and resources through appeals, reviews, and amendments in order to finally settle private matters, notwithstanding what Mr. Hob house and Chief Justice Gajendragadkar so sagely stated.[58] Every state's lower courts are bound by the rulings of the higher courts, which are obligated to uphold the laws proclaimed by the Supreme Court. [59] However, the highest court in the country is made up of independent judges who are not afraid to express their differing opinions. Emerson once said, 'A foolish consistency is the hobgoblin of little minds'.[60] Author went further discussing the lack of effective case law management, "A significant portion of the 27 million cases that are now outstanding[61] in Indian courts can be traced, at least in part, to this unusual Indian ailment, since the '*judgments factory*' has become excessively industrialized: '*case law diarrhea*'"[62]. Finally author provides suggestions for judicial reforms.[63] Author talks about the handling of criticism by the court itself has become so sensitive which is detrimental for judiciary itself and lawyers and judges should work to change it. The current state of the law of contempt in India is an impediment to judicial reform.[64] But till altered,[65] we must cope with it.[66]

C. Contribution

The book 'India's Legal System: Can It Be Saved?' by Fali S. Nariman approximately seven by four inches huge, may initially appears like a brief volume book but this book holds roller coaster of most important yet often overlooked topics. These are subjects that everyone should be familiar with, though many have not recognized their importance—until now. Author of this book has really well-researched before writing this book and every chapter every page contains information, knowledge and opinion with harsh reality. This book is well written

with some legal technicalities is somewhat can be typical for a layman to read who is not related to the field of legal profession. The clever and learned writer has recalled that "making a book is a specialty, as is making a clock; it takes more than mind to turn into a writer".

The concept of justice in *Manusmriti* lest we understand what Manusmriti is; "Justice, being violated, destroys; Justice, being preserved, preserves; Therefore, justice must not be violated; Lest violated justice destroy us".[67] Justice Krishna Iyer has revealed in many of his own judicial pronouncements: that our legal system (based on Anglo-Saxon jurisprudence), which we have adopted and adapted in this country does work: "*if you only know how to make is work*".[68] Make your decision in accordance with the law, however keep in mind that legislation without of justice resembles an egg devoid of its yolk and a large portion of the salt that it contains.[69] This book imposes big questions like; why the constitutional composers has not adopted a polity based on 'village autonomy and self-sufficiency'? If you discover this book, you will find more such questions and can debate over it, third millennium it is up to you to save the India's legal system! This book covers the understudies of law, constitution and political science.

Critique

The value contributed by the publication has been highlighted in the section above. While nothing in this part would negate that fact, the writer might have done better in a few specific areas. We experienced excessively long sentence developments which were complex to understand. While reading we lost track of it multiple times and had to re-read it several times to comprehend what is written. Author could have worked upon the language to keep the language layman and the sentences short.

Author whilst have expressed many problems of the legal system of India and has deeply analyzed them he does not offer solutions or address how these issues might be resolved, what should we do about those problems? How do we take care of the issue? Besides author has presented some topics in fragments, which as a reader obstructs us from drawing the final conclusion about that particular topic like; author has discussed about how the Supreme Court is the most important court and guides the law of this country, yet in another section, he critiques the inconsistencies in the Court's decisions, which sometimes divert or hinder justice. This fragmented approach leaves interpretation up to the reader. It would have been beneficial if the author had consolidated these discussions, drawing a clear conclusion to convey his perspective more directly. The tendency of author to not to draw the conclusions at the end of every chapter makes it difficult for us as a reader as to what should we learn, adapt, comprehend or apply from the chapter. Author could have framed the conclusion at the end of every chapter for readers convenience and retaining the information presented

Conclusion

Nariman shows the importance and need of understanding and saving the India's legal system. In our view, this book should be read by everyone, as there is a pressing need for the improvement of the country's legal framework. Mr. Fali S. Nariman has beautifully quoted that "In a democracy, every institution, including the judiciary, is accountable to the people in whose name it operates". Through this book author sends a powerful message to the third millennium urging efforts to reform the legal system of India.

We, through this review and analysis has paved a way for the layman and legal professional to either read this book or not and has opened the gates for opinion and discussion after post-reading of the book. It is our hope that every reader who engages with Mr. Nariman's work is inspired to reflect as deeply as we have. If a layman or a legal professional, wants to know the judicial system of India, he would good to refer to this book.

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